

Effect of Casting Parameters on the Mechanical Properties of Aluminum Alloy Matrix Composites Fabricated by the LPF Method

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ABSTRACT

Liquid Pressure Forming process (LPF method) is one of the most efficient methods for manufacturing MMCs, and has a number of advantages over the conventional squeeze casting method. These include minimized deformation of preforms and reduce damage to fibers during manufacture. We studied the effect of casting parameters on the mechanical properties of MMCs fabricated by the LPF method, and appeared that the Mg free MMCs, the MMCs with no binder and sintered preform, and Al-Cu matrix MMCs reveal high tensile strength.

INTRODUCTION

Because of the recent demands on high strength and light weight materials, especially for automobile parts, metal matrix composites (MMCs) have attracted considerable attention from a wide range of industrial sectors. Compared to powder metallurgy hot pressing and diffusion bonding, the liquid metal infiltration process is one of the most cost-effective techniques for fabricating MMCs. The reason for this is the casting technique allows the net or near-net shape production and a wide choice in the selection of the reinforcements and matrix alloys. Much work has been done on the squeeze casting process, but little has been done on the Liquid Pressure Forming (LPF) process.

The LPF process is one of the most efficient methods for manufacturing MMCs, and has a number of advantages over the conventional squeeze casting method. These include minimized deformation of preforms and reduce damage to fibers during manufacture. Other advantages of this process are:

1. The required pressure is significantly lower compared to squeeze casting.
2. Net-shape components can be produced.
3. Evacuation removes the trapped air in the preform.

To obtain high quality MMCs the process was optimized by adjusting parameters such as infiltration time, Mg contents in matrix, die temperature to name a few. We will present recent results from ongoing research on the parameters which significantly influence the micro- and macro structures and mechanical properties of the resulting composites in the LPF process.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

THE INFILTRATION PROCEDURES

The LPF process, schematically shown in Figure 1, is a method of liquid infiltration that uses pressurized air to force liquid metal into a preform of reinforcement material. The preform is loaded in a spirit die (Figure 1a). The shape and the size of the die are dictated by the component which is to be manufactured. The die cavity is connected to the crucible in a furnace with a feed tube which carries the liquid metal during infiltration. The crucible and the furnace are held in a pressure vessel. Once the preform is loaded, the die is closed and then the die cavity and the pressure vessel is evacuated (Figure 1b). Evacuation serves 2 purposes; degassing of the molten metal and removal of air in the die cavity and the preform. After evacuation, the air pressurized at 0.32 MPa is applied to the surface of the molten metal, forcing the molten metal to rise up through the feed tube (Figure 1c). The molten metal is then carried into the die cavity and infiltrates the preform. Once solidification is completed in casting, the pressurized gas is vented from the system and the casting is ejected from the split die (Figure 1d).

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the LPF process

The LPF method has more factors that affect the MMCs quality, compared with those of the squeeze casting, because of its low infiltration pressure. The matrix temperature is changed between 100 K and 230 K during superheat. The die temperature has two factors; one is a sprue temperature and the other is a temperature gradient between the sprue and the die-edge. The sprue temperature is fixed at 873 K and the temperature gradient (ΔT) is set at 50 K. The heaters in the die were on for the first 3 minutes of the process and then turned off.

MATRIX AND REINFORCEMENT

The preforms were aluminum-borate whisker ($9\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$) preforms, 22 mm-thick and 150 mm x 75 mm, with 25 % volume fraction whiskers. We used 3 types of preforms because the preform could be transformed or broken when the high-pressure melt was infiltrated. They are as follows:

I. No-binder preforms (written NB) that are fired 1173 K for 4 hours.

II. Binder preforms (written B) that are fired 1173 K for 4 hours using a few wt. % silica binder.

III. No-binder and sintered preforms that are sintered at 1573 K for 4 hours in order to strengthen with whiskers interactive sintering (written NB-H).

Preforms were preheated at 1173 K before they were loaded in the die cavity.

The matrix alloys (Table 1) were an eutectic Al-Si alloy (AC8A in JIS), a hyper-eutectic Al-Si alloy (AC9A in JIS) and an Al-Cu alloy (AC1B in JIS).

Table 1. Chemical composition of the matrix alloys

	(wt%)							
	Si	Cu	Mg	Ni	Mn	Fe	Ti	Al
AC1B	0.15~ 0.35	4.6~ 5.3	0.20~ 0.40	-	0.20~ 0.40	≤0.15	0.10~ 0.30	Bal.
AC8A	11.0~ 13.0	0.8~ 1.3	0.7~ 1.3	0.8~ 1.5	≤0.15	≤0.8	≤0.20	Bal.
AC9A	22~ 24	0.5~ 1.5	0.5~ 1.5	0.5~ 1.5	≤0.50	≤0.8	≤0.20	Bal.

STRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTY DETERMINATION

Macro- and micro-structures of MMCs were studied along the cross section, from the sprue to the die-edge using an optical microscope and a scanning electron microscope. Also, we used an image analyzer to measure the surface fraction of pores to determine porosity. Lastly, tensile tests were performed. Specimens were taken from the cross section plane from the sprue to the die-edge.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

THE EFFECT OF MATRIX COMPOSITION

Examination of the Al-Si matrix material revealed white bands in the center region of the composites as shown in Figure 2. These white bands seem to form at regions where the melt fronts meet each other. The width of these bands is less than 2 mm.

No micro-structural differences can be found between the white band (A in Figure 2) and the surrounding area (B in Figure 2). Macro segregation of Si and Mg, however, is found. In the white band, Mg decreases from 0.67 wt. % (surrounding sound area) to 0.55 wt. %, and Si decreases from 16.2 wt. % (surrounding sound area) to 14.4 wt. %. The tensile strength of the white band region is about 50 MPa lower than that of the surrounding sound region.

Figure 2. The white band observed in MMC

The tensile strength of MMCs increase with decreasing Mg content in the matrix and in fact, the Mg free alloy has the highest tensile strength of the MMCs investigated in this study (Figure 3). Also, it was observed that the contrast between the white band and the surrounding are decreases with decreasing Mg content. The mechanism for the formation of the white band is still unknown, however, it appears Mg must play an important role in its formation. Because of this finding, we studied the effect of casting parameters on the high strength, no white band, Mg free, MMC.

Variation in the MMCs tensile strength with matrix is shown in Figure 4. The improvement in tensile strength, due to reinforcement, is evident in all cases in Figure 4. It should be noted that the maximum tensile strength was achieved by the AC1B MMC. Also, the T6 heat treatment increases the tensile strength of the AC1B MMC, but appears to have reverse effect on the other two materials.

Figure 3. The effect of Mg contents on the tensile strength of MMCs.

Figure 4. Comparison of the tensile strength of different matrices.

THE EFFECT OF PREFORM MAKING PROCESS

As mentioned above, we used three types of preforms. Of these preforms, NB preforms have the highest strength while B preforms have the lowest strength. Before fire treatment, the whiskers show a smooth surface with no observable damage. In the NB and NB-H preforms, remarkable changes are not observed on the whisker surface after the fire treatment. However, it was observed that the whiskers in the NB-H preforms were sintered together (Figure 5(a)). This interactive sintering is thought to strengthen the preforms. In the NB preforms, sintering of the whiskers wasn't observed, but the whiskers did appear to contact each other through static electricity interactions. In the B preforms, many particles (probably SiO₂ binder) can be found on the whisker surface, and these binder particles are thought to connect whiskers (Figure 5(b)). Variation in the tensile strength of MMCs with preform is shown in Figure 6. The highest strength is given by NB preform MMC. However, after T6 heat treatment the NB-H preform MMC gives the highest tensile strength.

Figure 5. The SEM microphotographs of the whisker surface.
 (a) NB-H preform, (b) B preform, x 20000

Figure 6. Comparison of the maximum tensile strengths.

THE EFFECT OF LIQUID METAL TEMPERATURE

The higher melt temperature makes infiltration easier, however, the interactions between the melt and the whiskers are accelerated at high temperatures. These interactions prevent the rapid solidification of the melt. The tensile strength variations of composites versus superheat are shown in Figure 7. In AC1B matrix composites, high tensile strengths are obtained at 120 K and 150 K superheats. There is a peak in strength among the 120 - 150 K superheats. Infiltration was not complete at the 100 K superheat, and many defects on the order of 100 μ m were observed in the composites. The SEM microphotographs of extracted whiskers are shown in Figure 8. Reaction product was not observed on the whisker's surface for the 150 K superheat, but the whisker surfaces of the 200 K superheat showed significant amounts of reactant. These observed differences in the AC1B whisker's surface with superheat are thought to be caused by an interface reaction between the fibers and the matrix alloy above 150 K superheat.

Figure 7. The effect of superheat on the maximum tensile strengths.

On the other hand, no large effect of the superheat is found in the AC8A matrix composites. In these composites, many reactants were observed at all liquid metal temperatures. It is supposed that the interface reaction between the fiber and the matrix alloy occurs easily in Al-Si system MMCs in contrast to Al-Cu system MMCs.

Figure 8. The SEM microphotographs of extracted whiskers.
 (a) 150 K superheat, (b) 200 K superheat, x10000

THE EFFECT OF THE PRESSURE HOLDING TIME

The tensile strength and the amount of porosity within AC8A matrix MMCs as a function of pressure holding time is shown in Figure 9. The strength sharply increases within the first 15 seconds of holding, and then gradually increases with holding times. The porosity is gradually reduced to nearly zero percent with holding time. From these results, it is thought that the infiltration is finished within a few minutes holding time. However, this MMC exhibited small cracks inside. It seems that it needs for achieving sound MMCs, the clamping force on a preform caused by the incoming pressurized melt must be maintained until the central portion of MMC is fully solidified. To eliminate these cracks, the pressure holding time needs to be about 7 minutes, as indicated by our study, but the tensile strengths of these MMCs are scattered. It is assumed that the solidification of the central portion wasn't complete within 7 minutes. We tried holding at 15 minutes to improve the scatter in the tensile strength. Scattering of the tensile strength is decreased after 15 minutes holding, and the maximum tensile strength is not decreased. According to the numerical simulation, about 35 minutes are needed to complete the melt solidification. The regions of lower tensile strength have many

Figure 9. The effect of the pressure holding time on the tensile strength and the pore ratio.

micro pores on the order of a few micro meters, and there isn't any evidence of whisker damage, therefore, it is thought that the melt solidification was not complete in 15 minutes and the micro pores are a sort of micro shrinkage.

CONCLUSION

1. The LPF method fabricate the MMCs that maximum tensile strength is 530 MPa with T6 heat treatment.
2. The solute Mg injured MMCs soundness and the maximum tensile strength is obtained with Mg free matrices.
3. The binder in the preforms make MMCs inferior. NB-H preform is effective for the high strength MMCs.
4. The excess superheat of the melt has a harmful effect on the tensile strength of the Al-Cu alloy matrix composite but scarcely has a remarkable effect in the Al-Si system alloy matrix composite.